

Fibre kinking fracture toughness of laminates under combined compression and shear

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Overview of ply-level failure modes

(Laffan et al, 2012)

Schematic diagram of kink band formation

(Liu et al, 2023)

Compact Compression specimen

Layup: $[(90^\circ/\theta)_8/90^\circ]_s$

Mechanical properties of T700/LT-03A unidirectional laminae (GPa)

Longitudinal	Transverse	Shear	Major Poisson's ratio
123	8.44	3.78	0.33

Calculated laminate stiffnesses (GPa)

Off-axis angle	E_x	E_y	G_{xy}	ν_{xy}	ν_{yx}	E'
0°	69.484	62.707	3.780	0.045	0.04	30.77
3°	69.474	60.428	3.799	0.048	0.042	30.814
6°	69.445	54.567	3.858	0.058	0.046	30.948
10°	69.381	44.666	3.998	0.081	0.052	31.276
15°	68.283	33.606	4.278	0.123	0.059	31.939

Specimen and experiment setup

Schematics of the electromagnetic Hopkinson bar system

(b) the inductive and active coils, (c) high-speed camera, (d) limiter.

Field of view

- Decompose the displacement field

$$u_{crack} = u_I + u_{II} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{Bmatrix} u_1 + u'_1 \\ u_2 - u'_2 \end{Bmatrix} + \frac{1}{2} \begin{Bmatrix} u_1 - u'_1 \\ u_2 + u'_2 \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$\text{where } u'_i = u(x_1, -x_2)_i$$

- Dynamic J-integral method

$$J_M^{lam} = \sum_A \left\{ \left[(W_M + K_M) \delta_{1j} - \sigma_{Mij} \Delta u_{Mi} \right] \frac{\Delta q}{\Delta x_j} \Delta A \right\} + \sum_A \left[\rho \left(\ddot{u}_{Mi} \Delta u_{Mi} - \dot{u}_{Mi} \frac{\Delta u_{Mi}}{\Delta x_1} \right) \Delta A \right] \quad (M = I, II)$$

- Fibre fracture toughness along the loading direction

$$J_I^{fibre} = 2.125 \cdot J_I^{lam}$$

Stage 0
1us/frame

Epsilon Y

The closing displacement and load of pins

good symmetry

compression fracture process

Shear strain at crack initiation

Off-axis 0°

Off-axis 3°

Off-axis 6°

Off-axis 10°

Off-axis 15°

Fracture toughness increases with increasing off-axis angle.

Quasi-static

Quasi-static

High-rate loading

Thanks!

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